

IMPROVING THE MECHANISM FOR THE INTRODUCTION OF INTERNATIONAL QUALITY STANDARDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURAL EXPORTS

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Annotation

The article highlights the role of international standards in the extensive introduction of international quality standards in the provision of the population with quality food products and the production and export of organic and environmentally consumable products.

Key words: agricultural products, ecological products, organic products, import-export, international standards.

In recent years "...certain works are being carried out on the reform of the agrarian sector, in particular on improving the public administration system in the field, the widespread introduction of market relations, strengthening the legal basis of relations between agricultural products, processing and selling entities, attracting investments in the industry, introducing resource technologies and providing manufacturers of agricultural products with modern techniques"¹.

Ensuring its development by introducing modern technologies and technologies, innovation, as well as the achievements of advanced science into agriculture, which is considered one of the most important sectors in our country, remains one of the most pressing issues. "Many businessmen from Germany, the Netherlands, France, Great Britain, Italy, Poland, Oman, Pakistan, Russia, Turkey, Israel and other countries visited our country's stand to establish mutually beneficial cooperation with suppliers from Uzbekistan"².

Ensuring the quality and safety of the products and services produced in our republic and their coordination with the requirements of world standards is one of the main factors in winning the competition struggle. The further deepening of integrative processes, the need to produce products that can compete with the products offered by foreign manufacturers in domestic and foreign markets, as well as the requirements of consumers for the quality of products, are

¹ <https://lex.uz/docs/4567334>

² <https://east-fruit.com/uz/yangiliklar/fruit-logistica-2022-ozbekiston-qishloq-khozhligi-mahsuloti>

demanding to increase the quality of agricultural products, including the further development of the introduction of international standards into the industry.

Today, at the international level, the demand for improving the quality of food and today's competitiveness is increasing from year to year. Therefore, the role of the marketing service is of particular importance in improving the quality of products, growing products and ensuring a guaranteed safe supply chain. "In 2022, more than 978,000 quality management systems have been introduced in the world that meet the requirements of the ISO 9001:2015 standard, as well as more than 33,000 food safety management systems that meet the requirements of the ISO 22000:2005 standard"³.

Despite the expansion of the implementation of these standard systems, in local practice, scientific approaches to their widespread use in the activities of agricultural cooperatives agroclusters, farmers and farms, as well as Agrologistics systems have not developed sufficiently. Taking into account them, it is important to improve quality management systems to improve the competitiveness of fruit and vegetable products.

The adopted software measures for the development of the network should ensure the transition of production in agriculture to the path of rapid development, the food security of the Republic and self-sufficiency with the main types of food products. This leads to a significant increase in the volume of agricultural exports, primarily processed products, which are in high demand in the foreign market.

Considering the importance of the issues of quality and safety of agricultural products on a global scale, it shows that a lot of scientific research work is carried out in this area. Today, the international standards that are popular in World Agricultural Practice and are required in entering markets are organic agriculture (Organic Agriculture) and optimal agricultural practices (Good Agricultural Practices Good Agriculture Programm (GAP)), which seek to provide the following in modern agricultural management systems:

- sustainable use of Natural Resources, Land, Water and biodiversity;
- production of safe food products and non - food goods;
- concern about the prosperous marriage of farmers;
- concern for animal welfare;
- minimal environmental impact;
- market expansion;
- gaining the confidence of the consumer;

- ensuring competitiveness in the market.

The world population is 8.3 billion in 2024. per person, and 8.4 crore in 2030. it reaches the person, which puts before the countries of the world the tasks of adopting urgent measures to provide them with food. In maintaining the next Average world level of food production per capita (298 kg/year), in 2023 the World volume of fruit and vegetable production reached a minimum of 3.1 billion. tons, and in 2030-2.5 billion. the tonnage should be.

To set quality standards for agricultural products, both scientists and practitioners in other fields of science are required to have in-depth knowledge, depending on physiology, biology, chemistry, ecology, economics, and product character and final tasks.

In conclusion, on the basis of ways to ensure food safety and introduce international standards, the possibility of exporting agricultural products increases. Based on the above, the following is recommended regarding ensuring food security in Uzbekistan and the introduction of the Global G.A.P standard:

- the volume of exports of fruit and vegetable products in our country can be increased by 32% and 24%, respectively, at the expense of increasing the area of land allocated for the cultivation of fruit and berry products by 100% and the volume of investment in the cultivation of fruits and vegetables. It is worth noting that at present, the existing population employment in the network has increased, which, accordingly, is determined to lead to a decrease in labor productivity, and at its expense it is determined that 20% will lead to a decrease in the volume of exports of fruit and vegetable products.

- the implementation of quality standards, technical, sanitary, hygienic, phytosanitary, veterans, environmental and other requirements for fruit and vegetable products in the world markets within the framework of ISO 9001:2000 and ISO 22000:2005 standards is insufficient and requires the formation and development of a mechanism for introducing standards in the quality management system in our country using the necessary institutional conditions for

Due to the combination of natural and soil-climatic conditions, which are rare in the world in Uzbekistan, the most delicious and most useful fruits and vegetables in the world are grown only in our region, taking into account many years of self-centered experiments Global G.A.P. acceptable agricultural practices in Uzbekistan on the basis of the standard (Uz G.A.P.)development as

well as Global G.A.P. it is advisable to develop and put into practice the mechanism for introducing the standard.

List of literature used:

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2. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 18, 2020 "On additional measures to ensure the compliance of quality and safety indicators of agricultural products with international standards" PF-5995.
3. <https://www.iso.org/the-iso-survey.html>

